

Towards the development of a power-HiL platform for the evaluation of battery management systems in maritime transport applications

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Abstract—Battery energy storage systems (BESS) are fundamental for the development of modern maritime transportation electrification solutions. These big and complex electrical energy storage systems require constant monitoring and control to ensure a convenient operation, guaranteeing safety and achieving a prolonged battery life-cycle. The battery management system (BMS) electronic control unit (ECU) is in charge of such duties. As BMSs are difficult to be assessed, some international agents identify the relevance of developing reliable hardware-in-the-loop (HiL) solutions for maritime BMS testing. In this work, the set up of a power HiL (PHiL) platform is described. In particular, a real-time plant model, including modelling elements previously presented by the authors, is implemented for a Speedgoat PHiL system. The real-time emulator accounts for the electrical and thermal domains of a 2p12s battery module. Results are presented illustrating the correct operation of the hardware battery emulation.

Index Terms—HiL, lithium-ion, battery modelling, maritime transport.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the maritime transport sector represents around 13.5 % of emissions in the European transport sector, negatively contributing to the climate change problem [1]. Although such figures are apparently low when compared to the total, around 76 % of maritime fuel is heavy fuel oil [2], which is often of poor quality and has a heavy sulphur content [3]. This can produce harmful effects on human health [3]. Consequently, various countermeasures are being proposed by the industry, academia and stakeholders: (a) an increased utilisation of high-standard diesel engines [3], (b) the substitution of these fuel oils by biofuels or liquefied natural gas [2], (c) the addition of alternative ancillary power sources to reduce fuel consumption (kites, wing sails, flettner rotors, etc.) [4], [5], or (d) the partial or total electrification of ships [6]–[8], including zero-emission operation in harbour and inland water areas [9] and cold ironing capabilities [10].

Four power architectures with varying levels of electrification, i.e., diesel/electric propulsion, hybrid battery propulsion with distributed storage, hybrid with DC power distribution and full electric propulsion [11], are mainly being developed for multiple types of vessels. Here, battery energy storage systems (BESS), which are connected to the ship's AC or

DC grid, play a relevant role in supplying or recovering the required electrical power, providing peak saving (acting as a buffer), spinning reserve, fast power transients in support of generators, energy harvesting (recovering energy from cranes, drilling equipment, etc., or from renewable sources) or backup power [12]. As a result of such electrification measures, it is expected that short distance ferries could benefit from a fuel saving potential of up to 100 % (full electrification), while other type of vessels would exhibit lower but significant saving figures [12]: up to 30 % for fishing vessels and bulk vessels with cranes, or up to 15 % for tug boats, for example.

Battery management systems (BMS) are microcontroller based electronic circuits which are on charge of controlling and monitoring the operation of a BESS [13]. These elements are fundamental for ship electrification, as they are in charge of controlling charging/discharging processes, targeting extending the lifetime of the battery units. They are also responsible for monitoring the State-of-Charge (SoC) and State-of-Health (SoH) [13] of the battery modules, guaranteeing that the BESS always operates within a safe operating window. Hazardous events such as the thermal runaway phenomena [14] in battery cells must be avoided at all cost by hardware measures but also by BMS supervision, as fire is one, if not the most, risky event that can occur in a vessel.

The usage of BESS in shipping is thoroughly studied in a recent report of Det Norske Veritas (DNV), carried out for the European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA). A set of recommendations are provided to fill the gaps identified for the future development of more reliable maritime BESS systems [12]. One of the main safety recommendations of the report considers the assessment of BMSs. Being such a vital component for the battery safety properties, BMSs are yet overlooked in many cases, according to DNV, as they are difficult systems to be evaluated. For that reason, wider deployment of more detailed assessment practices for BESS, such as the development of hardware-in-the-loop (HiL) procedures, is highly encouraged, specially as a wide utilisation of machine learning based algorithms is envisioned for future BMS applications.

In HiL procedures, a fully digital real-time simulation of the plant to be monitored and/or controlled (in this case the

battery module) is commonly carried out using a dedicated hardware device [15]. The digital real-time simulator can be comprised by one or various CPUs and/or FPGAs that run the model. Analog and digital input/output channels are provided to interface the real-time model with the real-world Electronic control unit (ECU) under test. The advantages of HiL testing are: (a) the control hardware and algorithms can be tested in detail, also before having the physical battery module available, and (b) tests under destructive operating conditions can be carried out without jeopardizing any expensive hardware element.

Power-HiL (PHiL) pushes the HiL testing capabilities one step further [16]. In PHiL, real currents and voltages are generated by a dedicated hardware device, which is commanded by the real-time model of the battery system. This way, not only the algorithms running in the BMS microprocessors but all the sensors, printed circuit board (PCB) designs and additional electronics equipment can be tested, providing a comprehensive way of assessing the whole BMS electronic control unit solution and its corresponding active front end (AFE) PCB boards.

In the following, the BESS operating conditions for large hybrid ship are provided. Then, based on previous thermal and electrochemical models developed by the authors [17], [18], a PHiL battery emulator is set up. The model runs in a Speedgoat Baseline real-time machine, and is connected to a battery cell emulation (BCE) module, also manufactured by Speedgoat, which also generates the real-world battery cell voltages. The mathematical equations of the real-time model are summarized, which accurately describe both the electrical and thermal domains of the battery module. Real-time results are finally provided under quasi-real maritime BESS operating conditions, showing the correct performance of the developed PHiL emulator.

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE MARITIME HYBRID POWERING SYSTEM BASED ON BESS

A. Hybrid powering architecture

As advanced at the introduction section, many powering architectures exist for the partial or total electrification of vessels. In this work, the diesel-electric propulsion configuration, depicted in Fig. 1, is considered [11]. There, a set of BESS and diesel generators support the vessel's high-power AC grid. The grid is then in charge of supplying the onboard power consumption (loads) and the propulsion required by the ship, which is fully electrically supplied. This approach is highly beneficial from an environmental point of view, as not only emissions are reduced during sailing, but also full electric operation capabilities can be provided while moving near or inside the port, providing a zero emission solution when the vessel is close to highly inhabited areas [11].

B. Operating profiles

The amount of public data regarding real (or quasi-real) operating profiles of large vessels which incorporate diesel-electric propulsion technologies is limited. However, in [19] *Guimire et al.* provide valuable information regarding the

Fig. 1: Diesel-electric propulsion vessel architecture with AC grid.

Fig. 2: Operating profile of the BESS of a large cruise ship during 180 hours of operation (adapted from data published in [19]).

power consumption profiles of this type of hybrid power system. The aforementioned article considers a cruise ship, with the propellers and onboard load powering fed by two independent (but connectible) high-power AC grids, similar to the one depicted in Fig. 1. Each grid is sustained by one BESS and two diesel generators. A total amount of 10 MWh of installed batteries is considered. The power demanded by the vessel is provided for an operation lasting 180 hours [19]. The operating profile shows the power requirements of the ship during port operations, under calm sea, and also under moderate or rough sea conditions. The charging/discharging cycles of the BESS are also detailed (Fig. 2), which will be latter applied to the real-time battery emulator.

III. MODELLING OF THE BATTERY MODULE

A. Modelling approaches for lithium-ion battery cells in the electrical domain

There are several approaches available to model lithium-ion battery cells in the electrical domain, which can be mainly listed as [20]: physics-based models (PBM), semi-empirical models, and empirical or data driven models. Their basis and their convenience for real-time execution is discussed in the following lines.

1) *Physics based models:* In PBM, the physical and chemical reactions occurring inside the battery are mathematically modelled, leading to highly accurate results. In addition, this approach provides results which have a real physical meaning.

The Doyle-Fuller-Newman (DFN) model is a widely used lithium-ion cell modelling approach. It describes lithium diffusion dynamics within the solid electrode material and the electrolyte, as well as electric potentials across space and time. The model is governed by a set of non-linear partial differential equations [21]. However, this type of model is extremely computationally demanding, making it challenging for real-time implementation.

Fig. 3: Equivalent Randles electric circuit of a Li-ion battery.

A lower computational cost alternative is the single particle model (SPM), which simplifies the DFN model by assuming uniform lithium concentration within each electrode particle and neglecting electrolyte concentration gradients [20], [22]. This approximation holds well for moderate charge/discharge rates but may become inaccurate at high currents [22].

Although the real-time execution of the SPM is feasible, its main drawback relies on the fact that a good knowledge of the electrochemical reactions inside the batteries is required. This can be an obstacle for engineers that are not specialists in electro-chemistry. Thus, in general, the semi-empirical or empirical modelling approaches that are discussed below could be a more convenient option for field engineers and academics with a great focus on electronics.

2) *Semi-empirical models*: The most common semi-empirical modelling approach is the one based on an equivalent electrical circuit of a battery, commonly known as the Randles model [23]. It was originally proposed by J.E.B. Randles in 1947 to model rapid electrode reactions [24]. This model is commonly linked with electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) for the interpretation of the impedance spectrum of a battery [25].

Fig. 3 shows a second order Randles equivalent circuit used for battery modelling. Here, V_0 represents the open circuit voltage (OCV) of the cell, which is obtained in the cell's terminals after relaxation, R_0 represents the contributions from the current collectors, electrolyte, and contact/interface resistances, and R_j and C_j are the resistance and capacity of the tank circuits, with $j = \{1, 2\}$ [18], which set the electrode dynamics. All these parameters highly depend on the SoC, SoH (degradation phenomena) and internal temperature of the cell. In general, those relationships are obtained experimentally [26] and saved into look-up tables (LUT) for modelling purposes.

The following expression represents the dynamics of the voltages of the tank circuits in a discrete k -th sampling instant:

$$V_j(k+1) = e^{-\frac{T_s}{\tau_j}} \cdot V_j(k) + R_j \cdot (1 - e^{-\frac{T_s}{\tau_j}}) \cdot i(k), \quad (1)$$

where $\tau_j = R_j C_j$ is the time-constant of the j -th tank circuit.

This semi-empirical approach has a low computational cost and it is simple to implement. It is possible to use circuit-based model based design (MBD) tools such as Matlab/Simulink Simscape Battery [27] for an easy digital implementation of the equivalent Randles circuit.

3) *Empirical or data-driven models*: Data-driven models are being recently used as they are highly flexible and they do not require any physical knowledge of the battery [22]. In

Fig. 4: Battery module cooling in a tube bank arrangement.

these cases, the “model-free model” term is adopted, which means that the battery is treated as a black box with its inputs and outputs [22].

To generate the black box, a high amount of high quality data is required first. Then, various methods such as differential analysis methods, empirical and data-fitting techniques, or specially machine learning (ML) algorithms [28] can be used to build the black box. Consequently, the main drawback of the data driven modelling approach is that a large amount of data is required for building the black box.

Considering all the previous, the semi-empirical approach is adopted in this work to model each battery module cell's electrical performance, in real-time, within the Speedgoat microprocessor.

B. Modelling the battery module in the thermal domain

1) *Battery module thermal management principles*: As previously stated in section III-A2, the main modelling parameters of the electrical part of the battery module are temperature dependant (V_0 , R_0 , R_j and C_j). Thus, the characterization of the heat generation and the heat transfer phenomena within the battery module become extremely important to obtain an accurate representation of the system.

Heat transfer will depend on the layout of the cells and the cooling elements, and also on the used cooling technology. Forced air cooling, immersion cooling and indirect water cooling arise as the most popular cooling technologies for BESS thermal regulation [29]. Forced air cooling is a cost-effective solution when compared to liquid-based cooling, but it provides lower heat extraction capabilities. All in all, many real-world maritime battery systems such as the Corvus Orca, Dolphin NxtGen Energy, Dolphin Power and Blue Whale products [30] rely on forced air cooling. In this work, forced air cooling is also considered, where cylindrical cells are configured through a tube bank. Thus, tube bank related heat transfer formulations apply [31], [32] and need to be included.

2) *Thermal model of forced air-cooled cylindrical cells in a tube bank configuration*: A battery module with cylindrical lithium-ion cells in a 2 parallel 12 series (2p12s) tube bank configuration (Fig. 4) is considered here. The coolant (air) flows in horizontal direction. For the sake of simplicity, the developed model is limited to describe heat transfer in the radial direction of the cylinder, as it is significantly greater than the one in the axial direction [33]. In particular, the following equations describe heat transfer between cells:

$$C_c \frac{dT_{c,i}}{dt} = Q_i + \frac{T_{s,i} - T_{c,i}}{R_c}, \quad (2)$$

$$C_s \frac{dT_{s,i}}{dt} = \frac{T_{f,i} - T_{s,i}}{R_u} + \frac{T_{s,i} - T_{c,i}}{R_c} + Q_{cc,i}, \quad (3)$$

where i represents the cell-number, and T_s , T_c , and T_f are the temperatures at cell surface, core of the cell, and cooling fluid (air), respectively. R_c is the thermal resistance relating heat transfer between the core and the cell surface through the conduction phenomenon. Similarly, the thermal resistance R_u is related to heat transfer between the cell surface and the environment. C_c is the thermal capacity of the cell's interior, while C_s refers to the capacity corresponding to its coating. Q_i is the heat generated by the cell as a result of its operation. Neglecting entropy losses, it is calculated as:

$$Q = i(V_0 - V_t) = R_{cell} \cdot i^2, \quad (4)$$

where $R_{cell} \approx R_{int}$. For simplicity, only Joule heating losses are considered, as they are dominant under high load demanding conditions (note: a complete expression for calculating heat generation can be found in [34]). Finally, $Q_{cc,i}$ denotes the heat transfer between adjacent cells in the same series chain. This term is calculated as follows [17]:

$$Q_{cc,i} = \begin{cases} (T_{s,2} - T_{s,1})/R_{cc}, & i = 1, \\ (T_{s,i-1} + T_{s,i+1} - 2T_{s,i})/R_{cc}, & i = 2, \dots, n-1, \\ (T_{s,n-1} - T_{s,n})/R_{cc}, & i = n, \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where R_{cc} is an aggregate parameter representing the heat conduction resistance of the tab and other possible connections between cells, as well as the air gap [35]. It is assumed that there is no heat transfer between the two cells placed in parallel in the same line, as both have almost identical characteristics and are subjected to the same conditions (i.e., there is no temperature gradient between them).

Furthermore, the increase in coolant temperature, which is produced as it extracts heat from the two series cell chains placed in parallel is taken into account [17]:

$$T_{f,i} = \begin{cases} T_{f,in}, & i = 1, \\ T_{f,i-1} + 2 \cdot (T_{s,i-1} - T_{f,i})/(R_u C_f), & i = 2, \dots, n. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where C_f is the thermal conductance of the air and R_u is the resistance associated with the convection phenomenon. To calculate thermal capacity of air from its specific heat capacity, the mass flow-rate of air at the inlet can be defined as:

$$\dot{m} = \rho_f \cdot S_f \cdot v_f, \quad (7)$$

where ρ_f is the density of air, v_f is its velocity and S_f is the ventilation area.

When dealing with a material with low thermal conductivity, internal thermal gradients are expected to occur. Conversely, when working with highly conductive materials, it is reasonable to assume that internal resistance is insignificant, resulting in minimal or zero thermal gradients. This idea gives rise to the lumped thermal models, which assume that the temperature of a solid remains constant with position and only varies with time [33]. This idealization offers significant simplification for certain heat transfer problems without sacrificing too much

accuracy. A lumped thermal model can be applied if the dimensionless Biot number (Bi) is less than or equal to 0.1:

$$Bi = \frac{L_c \cdot h}{k} < 0,1 \quad (8)$$

$$L_c/k \ll 1/h, \quad (9)$$

where k is the heat transfer coefficient by cell conduction, h is the convective heat transfer coefficient, and $L_c = V/A_s$ is the characteristic length, where V is the volume of the solid and A its surface area.

This assumption can simply (2) and (3), resulting the following heat transfer equation:

$$\frac{dT_{s,i}}{dt} = \frac{h \cdot A_s}{m_{cell} \cdot c_{p,cell}} (T_{f,i} - T_{s,i}) + \frac{Q_{gen,i}}{m_{cell} \cdot c_{p,cell}} + \frac{Q_{cc,i}}{m_{cell} \cdot c_{p,cell}}, \quad (10)$$

where m_{cell} is the mass of each cell, and the first term on the right-hand side of the equation refers to heat transfer on the cell surface, which will primarily occur through convection.

Further details about the heat transfer model implementation and parameter calculations can be found in the conference publications [17] and [31].

IV. REAL-TIME RESULTS OBTAINED IN THE SPEEDGOAT-BCE PLATFORM

A. Hardware platform description

Fig. 5 shows the physical layout of the PHiL platform under development. The hardware platform consists of a Speedgoat Baseline real-time machine (item no. 1), a BCE developed by Speedgoat (item no. 2), a 48 V power supply that feeds the BCE power side (item no. 3), a 5 V supply to feed the regulation side of the BCE (item no. 4), a Yokowaga WT1806E precision power analyser (item no. 5), and additional security related elements. The Speedgoat Baseline real-time machine is connected via Ethernet to the terminal (user interface), and runs the battery module model described in section III in one of the computational cores of its microprocessor (Intel Celeron, 4 cores at 2 GHz).

The BCE communicates with the Speedgoat Baseline real-time system through EtherCAT, and physically generates the real-world voltages of the emulated battery module. In particular, this component is the model BCE12-0805. It is able to emulate up to 12 battery cell terminals. This way, a varying number of virtually paralleled cells (two in this case) can be assigned to each physically available emulation terminal. This way, a battery model, consisting on a 2p12s configuration with cylindrical lithium-ion cells, has been implemented.

The model has been developed in the Matlab/Simulink environment. The model based design (MBD) approach has been followed to build the model, and automatic code generation tools have been used to create the executable for the real-time system.

The real-time model running in the Speedgoat Baseline system executes with a sampling period of 100 ms. The output voltages are then updated within the BCE12-0805 at the same sampling rate. Table I summarizes the most relevant

Fig. 5: Physical layout of the Speedgoat-BCE platform.

TABLE I. Most relevant electrical parameters and features of the battery module simulated in real-time in the Speedgoat-BCE platform.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Open Circuit Voltage at 100 % SoC	$V_0(100)$	2.59 [V]
Open Circuit Voltage at 0 % SoC	$V_0(0)$	2.03 [V]
Nominal capacity	C	23 [Ah]
C-rate during charge	$C_{rate,ch}$	0.7C
Model sampling period	T_{sim}	100 [ms]
Main features		
Chemistry	Lithium-ion	
Layout	Cylindrical	

nominal electrical parameters of the emulated battery module. A comprehensive summary of all the thermal parameter data can be found in reference [17].

B. Battery emulation results

Fig. 6 shows the emulation results obtained for cell number 12 (latest cell with respect to the direction of the coolant flow) when considering a slice of the whole charging/discharging profile of a vessel's BESS [19], normalized to a single 2p12s battery module. Fig. 6(a) shows the current flowing through the module, computed within the real-time device, while Fig. 6(b) shows the evolution of the SoC of cell number 12. In this particular case, the SoC varies approximately between 25 % and a 60 % during the simulated charging/discharging cycles.

On the other hand, Fig. 6(c) shows the evolution of the temperature of cell number 12. Thanks to the action of the forced air cooling system, cell number 12, which is the one with the highest working temperature within the module, experiences very low temperature swings, keeping the operating temperature at around 25°C. This is specially desirable, as operating with temperatures of around 20°C to 40°C with low temperature swings constraints battery degradation and guarantees an extended life-cycle.

Finally, Fig. 7 shows the evolution of the terminal voltage V_t of cell number 12, physically provided by the Speedgoat BCE12-0805 and registered by the power analyser. This result demonstrates the correct operation of the power emulation hardware, which will be of capital importance for future PHIL implementations.

(a) Current circulating through a 2p12s module.

(b) SoC of module number 12.

(c) Evolution of core temperature of module number 12.

Fig. 6: Real-time emulation results obtained for a single cell under BESS varying charging/discharging operation.

Fig. 7: Terminal current of cell number 12, measured in the BCE terminals and physically registered using a data logger.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, which is based on electrochemical and thermal models previously developed by the authors, a PHIL battery emulation platform is set up in a Speedgoat-BCE system. Among the electrochemical modelling approaches reported in the literature, the one based on equivalent circuit modelling (equivalent Randles circuit) is selected for its low computational burden and particular cell data availability. As high complexity is usually problematic for real-time simulation, the thermal domain phenomena is modelled following a simplified lumped representation. Cell emulation through the BCE hardware is also demonstrated, as results equivalent to the ones obtained in off-line simulations are achieved.

The next steps towards the completion of the PHIL solution, which, at the date of the article submission were still under development, include:

- The inclusion of a printed circuit board (PCB), which interfaces the BCE with the physical BMS electronics to be tested.

- The implementation of the BMS algorithms into the target hardware (NXP S32K344EVB).

Finally, it is worth noting that the PHiL battery emulation platform is flexible. This development will allow emulating, in the future, other battery cells, once these are conveniently characterized and modelled.

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